

Marketing Mix Strategy (7P) in Increasing Community Interest at Man 1 Trenggalek

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ABSTRACT

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Madrasahs continue to improve the quality of their education in the competition to attract the public. This is also done by MAN 1 Trenggalek which has strategies for increasing the number of quality students. This research aims to describe in depth the marketing mix (7P) strategy of MAN 1 Trenggalek in increasing public interest. Researchers use qualitative research. Data collection techniques are in-depth interviews, participant observation and documentation. Data analysis starts from data condensation, data presentation, verification and drawing conclusions. The results of the research show that the marketing mix strategy (7P) is: 1) The products being marketed are quality madrasah graduates, able to compete and can be accepted at State Universities, State Islamic Universities, Service Schools, TNI/POLRI, Tahfidzul Qur' Islamic Boarding Schools an, and able to be absorbed into the world of work. 2) The price offered is an affordable education fee that does not burden the students' parents, there is PIP, the education fee is IDR 0.- (rupiah) for those who do not have PIP but have one of the welfare cards. Rewards from the madrasa committee for outstanding students. 3) The madrasa marketing place is a strategic madrasa location in the central area of Trenggalek Regency, close to the Trenggalek stadium, several Islamic boarding schools and other important places. 4) Promotion/promotion by introducing and showing the advantages of the madrasah to prospective students and parents via social media within the network (IG, Tiktok, Web and others) and outside the network by participating in competitions at district, provincial and national levels. 5) People in marketing madrasa education services are qualified educators, well-dressed, polite, neat and friendly. Madrasah Committee, Parents and people who have good hopes for the development of the madrasah. 6) Process/The marketing process is good communication between all madrasa parties jointly marketing by carrying out the stages of planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. 7) Physical Evidence/Physical Evidence consists of representative learning rooms, 3 language laboratories, computer laboratories, libraries, halls, teachers' rooms, TU rooms, UKS, canteen and sports fields.

KEYWORDS:

Marketing Mix (7P),
Public Animo

1. INTRODUCTION

Madrasah Islamic educational institutions are an educational organizing unit that has noble and dignified goals for the Indonesian nation, namely to guide students in pursuing education in accordance with the mandate of the pursuing education in accordance with the mandate of the 1945 Law. The progress of science, technology and

information in the world of Islamic education is one of the things that is of special concern and requires careful planning to produce graduates who are able to compete in the global era. Social life is influenced by various things, one of which is the field of education (Ngainun Naim, 2009). Madrasahs are non-profit educational institutions that operate in the field of educational services with the aim of serving consumers or users of educational services which include pupils, university students and the general public (Buchari Alma, 2005). Education is a service product produced by educational institutions, therefore when looking at the role of Islamic educational institutions it shows that the activities in Islamic educational institutions are production organizations that

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produce Islamic education services which are purchased and used by consumers of educational services. Excellent service to consumers of educational services aims to increase public trust and promote madrasas. So that madrasas are able to continue to maintain the quality and quantity of students.

An Islamic education marketing strategy is mandatory as a madrasa effort to introduce the institution to prospective new students or users of Islamic education services. Marketing Islamic education should be an activity in realizing the existence of Islamic educational institutions that continue to be known by the wider community while continuing to improve quality. Marketing of Islamic education is carried out while still paying attention to developments in science, technology and developments of the times so that it can be recognized and accepted by society in accordance with the existing times.

Marketing Islamic education begins by carrying out consumer analysis of Islamic education through a market segmentation process and identifying consumer behavior. This stage is the basis for finding out what the real needs and desires are and what the objective conditions of consumers of Islamic education services are. Based on the results of the analysis of the objective conditions of consumers of Islamic education services, a marketing mix will be developed using the marketing mix in the marketing process of Islamic education services to gain the interest of the public or consumers of Islamic education services. As a strategy for effective market control, the marketing mix strategy is often known as the 7Ps which include product, price, promotion, place, people, process and psychological evidence (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012).

Marketing strategies for Islamic educational institutions are very necessary in facing the era of competition and globalization which cannot be stopped and must be followed so that Islamic educational institutions continue to exist. The marketing strategy process for Islamic educational institutions helps in identifying what they want to achieve, as well as how to achieve the expected results. The role of marketing strategies for Islamic educational institutions is increasingly being recognized over time, especially nowadays. Every Islamic educational institution continues to be challenged and tested to compete with other Islamic educational institutions. Islamic educational institutions that are unable to maintain their institutional existence will be abandoned by the community using Islamic educational services or their market share so that Islamic educational institutions may close their gates. With the 7P marketing mix strategy, Islamic educational institutions will be able to understand their competitive abilities and develop sustainable competitive advantages systematically and consistently to increase public interest and trust, especially in entrusting their children to Islamic educational institutions.

Public trust in Islamic educational institutions is the key to the progress of Islamic educational institutions themselves. When the community or users of Islamic

education services have confidence in Islamic educational institutions, they will be accompanied by full support by entrusting their children and daughters to these Islamic educational institutions. Apart from that, users of Islamic education services will influence other people to do the same in the sense of promotion to other users of Islamic education services. This will be the opposite when the community or users of Islamic education services do not have confidence in an Islamic educational institution, the community will be reluctant to entrust their sons and daughters to that Islamic educational institution and even provoke other educational service users not to enroll their sons and daughters in educational institutions. Islam is because there is no confidence in the quality of an Islamic educational institution (Mujamil Qomar, 2007).

The researcher took the theme of MAN 1 Trenggalek's marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest. This election was due to increasing public interest in Islamic education. This happens because people choose Islamic educational institutions as their main choice in order to send their sons and daughters to study at Islamic educational institutions. Because currently Islamic educational institutions have also developed in the direction of technological and information advances. Interesting to research is how the marketing strategy carried out by MAN 1 Trenggalek increases public interest.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Strategy Concept

Buchari Alma (2011) wrote that Bittle explained that strategy is a fundamental plan to achieve company goals. As for KBBI, strategy is a careful plan regarding activities to achieve specific targets. Strategy is seen as a program that includes goals to be achieved, accompanied by specific actions or steps to achieve these goals in an effort to respond to the environment (KBBI, 2005).

Marketing is defined as a process of planning and carrying out concepts, prices, promotions and distribution of a number of ideas, goods and services to create exchanges that can satisfy individual and organizational goals (Graham, 2008). Marketing is an organization of functions and a series of processes for creating, communicating and providing value to customers and managing customer relationships in a way that benefits the organization and its stakeholders (AMA, 2010). Meanwhile, Kotler and Keller (2012) define marketing as a social process for individuals and groups to get what they need and want by creating, offering and freely exchanging products and services that have value with other parties.

According to Mc Charty (2015) that marketing strategy is a way of determining the target market and marketing mix related to the product. This is a big picture of what the company will do in several markets. There are two things that are interrelated with marketing strategy, namely: (1) the target market is a homogenous (similar) group of customers to whom the company wants to appeal; (2)

marketing mix, namely the controlled variables that the company combines to satisfy the company's target group. A marketing strategy is a plan that is specifically formulated systematically regarding marketing activities which is used as a guide for the implementation of marketing variables such as market identification, market segmentation, market positioning and marketing mix elements and other things related to marketing.

B. Education Services Marketing Mix

Marketing mix is a combination of four variables, namely product, price structure, promotional activities, and distribution system. The four elements of the marketing mix are interrelated and influence each other, therefore efforts must be made to produce a marketing policy that leads to effective service and is centered on consumer satisfaction. Therefore, in the marketing mix there are variables that support each other, then the company combines them into a single unit in order to get the desired responses in the target market.

The marketing environment consists of a micro environment and a macro environment. The micro marketing environment consists of companies, suppliers, intermediaries, consumers and competitors. Meanwhile, the macro marketing environment includes broader social forces that influence the micro environment; including demographic, economic, natural, technological, political and cultural (Kotler and Keller, 2009). The marketing mix is marketing elements that are interrelated, mixed, organized and used appropriately and efficiently so that the company can achieve marketing objectives effectively, while providing satisfaction of consumer needs and desires. So that in the marketing mix the marketing elements are interrelated and organized, so that the company is able to produce effective, efficient marketing and achieve marketing goals effectively and efficiently (Hurriyati, 2010).

The marketing mix concept according to Kotler and Keller (2002) consists of 7Ps. The service marketing mix in question is the 7P concept, namely:

a. *Product*

A product is something that can be offered to the market to get attention, so that the product being sold will be purchased, used or consumed and can fulfill a consumer's desire or need. A product is anything that a producer can offer to be noticed, requested, searched for, purchased, used or consumed by the market to fulfill the needs or desires of the relevant market.

b. *Price*

Price is the amount of value that consumers exchange for the benefits of owning or using a product or service whose value is determined by the buyer and seller through bargaining, or set by the seller at the same price for all buyers. Price is the only element of the marketing mix that provides

income or income for the company, while the other three elements (product, distribution and promotion) cause costs (expenses). Besides that, price is an element of the marketing mix that is flexible, meaning it can be changed quickly. This is different with product characteristics or commitment to distribution channels. These two things cannot be changed or adjusted easily and quickly, because they involve long-term decisions.

c. *Place*

Place is a place associated as a distribution channel aimed at reaching target consumers. This distribution system includes location, transportation, warehousing, and so on. Distribution can be defined as an activity that seeks to expedite and facilitate the delivery of goods and services from producers to consumers, so that their use is in accordance with what is needed (type, quantity, price, place and when needed).

d. *Promotion*

Promotion means activities that convey the benefits of a product and persuade customers to buy it. Promotion is one of the determining factors for the success of a marketing program. Regardless of the quality level of a product, if consumers have never heard of it and are not sure that the product will be useful to them, they will never buy it. The importance of promotion can be illustrated through the parable that marketing without promotion can be likened to a man wearing black glasses who from a dark place on a dark night winks at a beautiful girl in the distance. No one knew what the man was doing, apart from himself. Sales promotion objectives originate from marketing communications. The specific objectives determined for sales promotions vary, depending on the type of target market. For companies, these goals include efforts to encourage consumers to use more products, buy products in larger units and try products promoted by the company.

e. *People*

Human Resources are people who are involved in the marketing process or delivery of educational services to educational service users or consumers and influence them to continue to entrust education providers in educating their sons and daughters (Buchari Alma, 2008). So the role of people in marketing educational services is a basic and important part of conveying information about educational service providers. Apart from influencing users of educational services, Human Resources are people who are involved in the process of improving and creating quality Islamic educational institutions.

f. *Process*

Process is a procedure, mechanism and series of activities in delivering products in the form of goods or services from producers to consumers or users (Buchori Alma, 2008). So the process is an influential factor in the marketing process, especially products in the form of services. This is because service users are actively involved in the fulfillment process and are part of the service itself. So it will be felt and clearly seen if there are any imperfections in the process.

g. *Physical Evidence*

Physical Evidence is the physical environment where educational service products are created and directly interact with consumers. In the marketing mix concept there are two first physical evidence, namely the design and layout of buildings such as premises/classrooms, laboratories, halls and others. The second supporting evidence which is an added value if it stands alone will not play any role such as student notes, report cards, award certificates. as well as other things.

C. Public Animo

Animo is a strong desire to do, do, or follow something. Animo is also often interpreted as someone's interest in something. The Big Indonesian Dictionary explains that animo means liking (inclination) for something, as well as desire. According to Mulyasa (2003) interest is a person's tendency to do something. Meanwhile, according to Winkel (1984) interest is a persistent tendency in a subject to feel interested in certain things and feel happy being involved in that field. So that interest has an element of the desire to know and study the desired object as an insight into knowledge for himself, the person will take real action to know and learn about something he wants as a need. Therefore, interest or what is also called a person's desire for something they aspire to, is the result of conformity between conditions and situations and expected needs.

Based on the several definitions above regarding interest, it can be concluded that interest is a desire that tends to remain in an individual to direct a particular choice which is believed to be a need, then continues to be realized in real action by paying attention to the object in question. he wants.

III. RESULTS

The findings from research at MAN 1 Trenggalek regarding the 7P marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest are as follows:

a. Product as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes graduates who are accepted at State Universities, State Islamic Universities, Official Schools, TNI POLRI, Tahfidzul Qur'an Islamic Boarding School, able to be absorbed into the world of work and other things that have benefits for other people. Apart from that, in achieving quality graduates who are able to compete, the products offered are student-oriented curriculum,

effective and efficient management of educators and educational staff, student management that focuses on students and management of facilities and infrastructure that considers adequacy, suitability and updates in line with developments over time.

- b. Price as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes educational costs that are affordable and not burdensome for students, PIP scholarships, rewards from the madrasah committee for outstanding students in the form of free one semester tuition fees, free LKS fees and others as a form of appreciation for outstanding students. Education fee relief program for orphaned and orphaned students. For students who have KIP, PKH, KKS but do not get PIP, the monthly education fee is free.
- c. Place as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes strategic madrasa locations, namely in the central area of Trenggalek district which is easy to reach. The location is close to the Trenggalek stadium, several Islamic boarding schools which can be used as boarding alternatives for students who study while boarding.
- d. Promotion as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes promotion by introducing the madrasa to prospective students via social media (IG, Tiktok, Web and others). Apart from that, taking part in competitions at district, provincial and national levels to continue to show the existence of the madrasa and promote it to the community.
- e. People as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes qualified educators, good appearance, polite, neat and friendly. Friendliness of educators and education staff in the learning process at the madrasah by getting used to shaking hands, greetings, saying hello and smiling. So as to create comfort in learning. Apart from that, educators and educational staff are the main agents in the process of marketing madrasas to the general public, assisted by the Madrasah Committee, Student Guardians, and people who have good hopes for the development of madrasas.
- f. The process as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes good communication between all madrasah parties to jointly market the madrasah by explaining to potential users of educational services, so that they are confident in the madrasah to educate their sons and daughters to become a generation of the nation that is quality, tough and has a global perspective.

Physical Evidence as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes representative learning rooms, 3 language laboratories, adequate computer laboratories, libraries, halls, teachers' rooms, TU rooms, UKS, canteen and representative sports field

The increase in public interest at MAN 1 Trenggalek is evidenced by the increase in the number of students as depicted in the following diagram:

Data on Graduates Continuing Education

Data on Educators and Education Personnel

No	Status	Amount	Graduate Of				
			SMP	SMA	D3	S1	S2
1	Teacher	77				64	13
2	Education Personnel	19	1	4	2	12	

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Product as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

The product as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes graduates who are able to compete to continue in state universities, both general and Islamic. Able to enter official school education, TNI POLRI, and the world of work. According to Kotler and Keller (2012), a product is something that can be offered to the market to gain attention, so that the product being sold will be purchased or consumed by consumers.

B. Price as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

Price as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes affordable education costs and relief for less fortunate students. The existence of PIP helps students to continue learning. If someone does not have PIP but has PKH, KKS and other welfare cards, then no education fees are charged, in other words IDR 0.- (rupiah). Price is the amount of value that consumers exchange for the benefits of owning or using a product or service whose value is determined by the buyer and seller through bargaining, or set by the seller at the same price for all buyers. As for the price in a school, it is a provision on the amount of financing that

must be spent by the student's parents in the learning process (receiving educational services) at that school. According to Kotler (2012) price consists of a list of prices Discounts Allowances Payment period Credit terms. The form of price is in the form of a price list, discounts, allowances, payment periods, credit terms. So the price in the marketing mix strategy carried out by madrasas is various activities related to determining the price (amount of cost) of education. Various forms of financing determination and payment processes are required.

C. Place as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

Place as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest is a very strategic madrasa location in the center of Trenggalek district and close to the stadium (sports center) and Islamic boarding school around the madrasa which allows students to go to school and live in the Islamic boarding school. This places the place as a distribution channel aimed at consumers. If it is an educational institution, the place is a place for distributing educational services, this includes classroom buildings, laboratories and other learning facilities.

According to Kotler (2012), related to place, it states that distribution channels consist of a set of institutions that carry out all activities (functions) used to distribute products and the status of their owners from producers to consumers. From the definition above, it can be interpreted that the distribution channel for an item is the entire activity or function of moving the product along with the owner's rights from the producer to the final consumer or industrial user. If related to educational institutions, place relates to the means of transferring educational services from school administrators to students.

D. Promotion as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest.

Promotion as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest by using online media in accordance with current developments such as TikTok, Instagram, websites and YouTube. Even though promotions are still done manually from one person to another. Promotion is an activity that conveys the benefits of a product and persuades customers to buy it. In educational institutions, promotion is the task of public relations, which has the role of conveying information needed by the community, especially students and parents, related to educational information.

According to Kotler (2012) Promotion is an important thing for educational institutions, this is if in companies it is a form of advertising, whereas in educational institutions promotion is used to convey or socialize existing programs in educational institutions so that they are known to the public. Promotion is the activity of communicating information from sellers to consumers or other parties in the sales channel to influence attitudes and behavior. In

educational institutions, promotions are handled by the deputy principal for public relations.

E. People institutions as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

People as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest are actors in the marketing process of educational services. So that the entire madrasah academic community must play an active role in implementing the marketing of educational services. Starting from teaching staff and educational staff. The human resources possessed by madrasahs are superior human resources and many graduates from well-known universities in Indonesia. So apart from being responsible for marketing the madrasah. Human resources must be maximized in implementing learning so that graduates can achieve maximum results.

F. Process as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

Process as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest is a way for all madrasah elements to play an important role in the marketing process of educational services. This starts from planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. This step is important because sometimes many things are forgotten about the series of processes in marketing educational services.

G. Physical Evolution as a marketing mix strategy to increase public interest

Process as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes physical evidence to support the product being marketed. In the world of education, this includes adequate facilities and infrastructure including classrooms, halls, auditoriums, libraries, offices and other infrastructure.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusions of the 7P marketing mix strategy to increase public interest at MAN 1 Trenggalek include:

- a. The products being marketed include quality madrasah graduates who are able to compete and can be accepted at State Universities, State Islamic Universities, Service Schools, TNI POLRI, Tahfidzul Qur'an Islamic Boarding Schools, and are able to be absorbed into the world of work.
- b. The price offered is an affordable education fee that is not burdensome to the students' parents. With PIP, the education fee is IDR 0.- (rupiah) for those who do not have PIP but have one of the welfare cards. Rewards from the madrasah committee for outstanding students as a form of appreciation for outstanding students.
- c. The marketing place for educational services is a strategic madrasah location because it is in the central area of Trenggalek district. The location is close to the Trenggalek stadium, several Islamic boarding schools and other places.

- d. Promotion/ promotion by introducing and showing the advantages of the madrasah to prospective students and parents via social media (IG, Tiktok, Web and others). Participate in competitions at district, provincial and national levels.
- e. People in marketing madrasah education services are qualified educators, well-dressed, polite, neat and friendly. Educators and educational staff are the main agents in the madrasah marketing process to the general public, assisted by the Madrasah Committee, Student Guardians, and people who have good hopes for the development of the madrasah.
- f. The process of marketing educational services is good communication between all madrasah parties to jointly market the madrasah by explaining to potential users of educational services, so that they are confident in the madrasah to educate their sons and daughters to become a generation of the nation that is quality, tough and has a global perspective.
- g. Physical Evidence as a marketing mix strategy in increasing public interest includes representative learning rooms, 3 language laboratories, adequate computer laboratories, libraries, halls, teachers' rooms, TU rooms, UKS, canteen and representative sports fields.

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